
**Non-Archimedean John, Non-Archimedean Dvoretzky-Milman, Non-Archimedean
Type-Cotype and Non-Archimedean Kwapien Problems**

K. MAHESH KRISHNA

School of Mathematics and Natural Sciences
Chanakya University Global Campus
NH-648, Haraluru Village
Devanahalli Taluk, Bengaluru North District
Karnataka State, 562 110, India
Email: kmaheshak@gmail.com
Date: March 11, 2026

Abstract: We ask for non-Archimedean version of following four: (1) John Theorem, (2) Dvoretzky-Milman Theorem, (3) Type-Cotype of Banach space, (4) Kwapien Theorem.

Keywords: John Theorem, Dvoretzky Theorem, Type-Cotype of Banach space, Kwapien Theorem.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2020): 47B10, 47L20, 12J25, 46S10.

1. NON-ARCHIMEDEAN JOHN AND DVORETZKY-MILMAN PROBLEMS

Let \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} be two finite dimensional normed linear spaces having same dimension. The **Banach-Mazur distance** between \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} is defined as

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}) := \inf\{\|T\|\|T^{-1}\| : T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y} \text{ is invertible linear operator}\}.$$

For $d \in \mathbb{N}$, let $(\mathbb{R}^d, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ be the standard Euclidean space. Famous John's theorem says following.

Theorem 1.1. [1, 14] (*John Theorem*) *If \mathcal{X} is any d -dimensional real normed linear space, then*

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{X}, (\mathbb{R}^d, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)) \leq \sqrt{d}.$$

Following surprising result says that every finite dimensional normed linear space has a subspace which is close (in the Banach-Mazur distance) to Euclidean space [6].

Theorem 1.2. [1, 6, 27] (*Dvoretzky-Milman Theorem*) *There is a universal constant $C > 0$ satisfying the following property: If \mathcal{X} is any d -dimensional real Banach space and $0 < \varepsilon < \frac{1}{3}$, then for every natural number*

$$k \leq C \frac{\varepsilon^2}{|\log \varepsilon|} \log d,$$

there exists a k -dimensional subspace \mathcal{Y} of \mathcal{X} such that

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{Y}, (\mathbb{R}^k, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)) < 1 + \varepsilon.$$

We refer [4, 7–10, 10–13, 23, 24, 26–28, 28, 31–33, 35] for more information on Dvoretzky-Milman theorem.

Let \mathbb{K} be a field. A map $|\cdot| : \mathbb{K} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called as a non-Archimedean valuation if following conditions are satisfied.

- (i) If $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}$ is such that $|\lambda| = 0$, then $\lambda = 0$.
- (ii) $|\lambda\mu| = |\lambda||\mu|$ for all $\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{K}$.
- (iii) (Ultra-triangle inequality) $|\lambda + \mu| \leq \max\{|\lambda|, |\mu|\}$ for all $\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{K}$.

In this case, \mathbb{K} is called as a non-Archimedean valued field [34]. Let \mathcal{X} be a vector space over a complete non-Archimedean valued field \mathbb{K} with valuation $|\cdot|$. A map $\|\cdot\| : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called as a non-Archimedean norm if following conditions holds.

- (i) If $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is such that $\|x\| = 0$, then $x = 0$.
- (ii) $\|\lambda x\| = |\lambda|\|x\|$ for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{K}$, for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$.
- (iii) (Ultra-norm inequality) $\|x + y\| \leq \max\{\|x\|, \|y\|\}$ for all $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$.

In this case, \mathcal{X} is called as a non-Archimedean linear space (NALS) [29]. Let \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} be finite dimensional non-Archimedean Banach spaces having same dimension. The non-Archimedean Banach-Mazur distance between \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} is defined as

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}) := \inf\{\|T\|\|T^{-1}\| : T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y} \text{ is invertible linear operator}\}.$$

Given $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and a non-Archimedean valued field \mathbb{K} , the standard vector space \mathbb{K}^n is a non-Archimedean linear space equipped with norm

$$\|(\lambda_j)_{j=1}^n\| := \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |\lambda_j|, \quad \forall (\lambda_j)_{j=1}^n \in \mathbb{K}^n.$$

Problem 1.3. (Non-Archimedean John Problem) Let \mathcal{K} be the set of all complete non-Archimedean valued fields. What is the best function $\Psi : \mathcal{K} \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following property: If \mathcal{X} is any d -dimensional non-Archimedean normed linear space over \mathbb{K} , then

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{X}, (\mathbb{K}^d, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)) \leq \phi(\mathbb{K}, d).$$

Problem 1.4. (Non-Archimedean Dvoretzky-Milman Problem) Let \mathcal{K} be the set of all non-Archimedean valued fields. What is the best function $\Psi : \mathcal{K} \times (0, \infty) \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following property: If \mathcal{X} is any d -dimensional non-Archimedean normed linear space over a non-Archimedean valued field \mathbb{K} and $\varepsilon > 0$, then for every natural number

$$k \leq \Psi(\mathbb{K}, \varepsilon, d),$$

there exists a d -dimensional subspace \mathcal{Y} of \mathcal{X} such that

$$d_{BM}(\mathcal{Y}, (\mathbb{K}^d, \|\cdot\|)) < 1 + \varepsilon.$$

2. NON-ARCHIMEDEAN TYPE-COTYPE AND KWAPIEN PROBLEMS

Let \mathcal{H} be a Hilbert space and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then for $h_1, \dots, h_n \in \mathcal{H}$, we have the generalized parallelogram identity

$$(1) \quad \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{-1, 1\}} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n \varepsilon_j h_j \right\|^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \|h_j\|^2.$$

On the other hand, the celebrated Jordan-von Neumann result says that Equality (1) characterizes the Hilbert space [17]. Equality (1) motivated the definition of Type and Cotype for Banach spaces.

Definition 2.1. [1] Let $1 \leq p \leq 2$. A Banach space \mathcal{X} is said to be of (**Rademacher**) **Type** p if there exists $T_p(\mathcal{X}) > 0$ such that

$$\left(\frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{-1, 1\}} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n \varepsilon_j x_j \right\|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq T_p(\mathcal{X}) \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \|x_j\|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad \forall x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathcal{X}, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Non-Archimedean John, Non-Archimedean Dvoretzky-Milman, Non-Archimedean Type-Cotype and Non-Archimedean Kwapien Problems

Definition 2.2. [1] Let $2 \leq q < \infty$. A Banach space \mathcal{X} is said to be of **(Rademacher) Cotype q** if there exists $C_q(\mathcal{X}) > 0$ such that

$$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n \|x_j\|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \leq C_q(\mathcal{X}) \left(\frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n \in \{-1, 1\}} \left\| \sum_{j=1}^n \varepsilon_j x_j \right\|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}, \quad \forall x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathcal{X}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

There is a vast literature on Type-Cotype of Banach spaces, see [1, 5, 15, 16, 20–22, 25, 30, 36]. In 1972, Kwapien proved the following breakthrough result using Type-Cotype notions [19].

Theorem 2.3. [19, 37] (**Kwapien Theorem**) A Banach space \mathcal{X} has Type 2 and Cotype 2 if and only if it is isomorphic to a Hilbert space.

We ask for non-Archimedean version of previous Type-Cotype and Kwapien theorem as follows. Let \mathbb{K} be a complete non-Archimedean valued field. Define

$$c_0(\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{K}) := \{ \{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty} : x_n \in \mathbb{K}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |x_n| = 0 \}.$$

Then $c_0(\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{K})$ is a non-Archimedean Banach space w.r.t. the norm

$$\| \{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty} \| := \max_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |x_n|, \quad \forall \{x_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty} \in c_0(\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{K}).$$

The space $c_0(\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{K})$ is very important (among other non-Archimedean Banach spaces) and is known as p -adic Hilbert space, see [2, 3, 18].

Problem 2.4. (Non-Archimedean Type-Cotype and Non-Archimedean Kwapien Problems) Whether there is a way to define non-Archimedean Type and non-Archimedean Cotype for non-Archimedean Banach spaces which will characterize the standard non-Archimedean Banach spaces $c_0(\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{K})$? i.e., whether we have a non-Archimedean Kwapien theorem?

REFERENCES

- [1] Fernando Albiac and Nigel J. Kalton. *Topics in Banach space theory*, volume 233 of *Graduate Texts in Mathematics*. Springer, 2016.
- [2] Paolo Aniello, Stefano Mancini, and Vincenzo Parisi. Trace class operators and states in p -adic quantum mechanics. *J. Math. Phys.*, 64(5):45, 2023.
- [3] Paolo Aniello, Stefano Mancini, and Vincenzo Parisi. Quantum mechanics on a p -adic Hilbert space: foundations and prospects. *Int. J. Geom. Methods Mod. Phys.*, 21(10):36, 2024.
- [4] Shiri Artstein-Avidan, Apostolos Giannopoulos, and Vitali D. Milman. *Asymptotic geometric analysis. I*, volume 202 of *Math. Surv. Monogr.* Providence, RI: American Mathematical Society (AMS), 2015.
- [5] Joe Diestel, Hans Jarchow, and Andrew Tonge. *Absolutely summing operators*, volume 43 of *Cambridge Studies in Advanced Mathematics*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1995.
- [6] Aryeh Dvoretzky. Some results on convex bodies and Banach spaces. In *Proc. Internat. Sympos. Linear Spaces (Jerusalem, 1960)*, pages 123–160. Jerusalem Academic Press, Jerusalem; Pergamon, Oxford, 1961.
- [7] T. Figiel. Some remarks on Dvoretzky’s theorem on almost spherical sections of convex bodies. *Colloq. Math.*, 24:241–252, 1971/72.
- [8] T. Figiel. A short proof of Dvoretzky’s theorem. In *Séminaire Maurey-Schwartz 1974–1975: Espaces L^p , applications radonifiantes et géométrie des espaces de Banach, Exp. No. XXIII*. 1975.
- [9] T. Figiel. A short proof of Dvoretzky’s theorem on almost spherical sections of convex bodies. *Compositio Math.*, 33(3):297–301, 1976.
- [10] T. Figiel, J. Lindenstrauss, and V. D. Milman. The dimension of almost spherical sections of convex bodies. *Acta Math.*, 139(1-2):53–94, 1977.
- [11] Y. Gordon, O. Guedon, and M. Meyer. An isomorphic Dvoretzky’s theorem for convex bodies. *Studia Math.*, 127(2):191–200, 1998.

-
- [12] Yehoram Gordon. Some inequalities for Gaussian processes and applications. *Isr. J. Math.*, 50:265–289, 1985.
- [13] Yehoram Gordon. Gaussian processes and almost spherical sections of convex bodies. *Ann. Probab.*, 16(1):180–188, 1988.
- [14] Fritz John. Extremum problems with inequalities as subsidiary conditions. Studies Essays, pres. to R. Courant, 187–204 (1948)., 1948.
- [15] W. B. Johnson and J. Lindenstrauss, editors. *Handbook of the geometry of Banach spaces. Vol. I.* North-Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 2001.
- [16] W. B. Johnson and J. Lindenstrauss, editors. *Handbook of the geometry of Banach spaces. Vol. 2.* North-Holland, Amsterdam, 2003.
- [17] P. Jordan and J. von Neumann. On inner products in linear, metric spaces. *Ann. Math. (2)*, 36:719–723, 1935.
- [18] G. K. Kalisch. On p -adic Hilbert spaces. *Ann. Math. (2)*, 48:180–192, 1947.
- [19] S. Kwapien. Isomorphic characterizations of inner product spaces by orthogonal series with vector valued coefficients. *Stud. Math.*, 44:583–595, 1972.
- [20] Rafal Latała and Krzysztof Oleszkiewicz. On the best constant in the Khinchin-Kahane inequality. *Studia Math.*, 109(1):101–104, 1994.
- [21] Daniel Li and Herve Queffelec. *Introduction to Banach spaces: analysis and probability. Vol. 1*, volume 166 of *Cambridge Studies in Advanced Mathematics*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2018.
- [22] Daniel Li and Herve Queffelec. *Introduction to Banach spaces: analysis and probability. Vol. 2*, volume 167 of *Cambridge Studies in Advanced Mathematics*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2018.
- [23] J. Matousek. *Lectures on discrete geometry*, volume 212 of *Graduate Texts in Mathematics*. Springer-Verlag, New York, 2002.
- [24] Ivan Matsak and Anatolij Plichko. Dvoretzky’s theorem by Gaussian method. In *Functional analysis and its applications*, volume 197 of *North-Holland Math. Stud.*, pages 171–184. Elsevier Sci. B. V., Amsterdam, 2004.
- [25] Bernard Maurey. Type, cotype and K -convexity. In *Handbook of the geometry of Banach spaces. Volume 2*, pages 1299–1332. Amsterdam: North-Holland, 2003.
- [26] V. Milman. Dvoretzky’s theorem—thirty years later. *Geom. Funct. Anal.*, 2(4):455–479, 1992.
- [27] V. D. Milman. A new proof of A. Dvoretzky’s theorem on cross-sections of convex bodies. *Funkcional. Anal. i Priložen.*, 5(4):28–37, 1971.
- [28] Vitali D. Milman and Gideon Schechtman. *Asymptotic theory of finite-dimensional normed spaces*, volume 1200 of *Lecture Notes in Mathematics*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1986.
- [29] C. Perez-Garcia and W. H. Schikhof. *Locally convex spaces over non-Archimedean valued fields*, volume 119 of *Camb. Stud. Adv. Math.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [30] Gilles Pisier. *Factorization of linear operators and geometry of Banach spaces*, volume 60 of *Reg. Conf. Ser. Math.* Providence, RI: American Mathematical Society (AMS), 1986.
- [31] Gilles Pisier. Probabilistic methods in the geometry of Banach spaces. In *Probability and analysis (Varenna, 1985)*, volume 1206 of *Lecture Notes in Math.*, pages 167–241. Springer, Berlin, 1986.
- [32] Gilles Pisier. *The volume of convex bodies and Banach space geometry*, volume 94 of *Cambridge Tracts in Mathematics*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1989.
- [33] Gideon Schechtman. A remark concerning the dependence on ϵ in Dvoretzky’s theorem. In *Geometric aspects of functional analysis (1987–88)*, volume 1376 of *Lecture Notes in Math.*, pages 274–277. Springer, Berlin, 1989.
- [34] W. H. Schikhof. *Ultrametric calculus. An introduction to p -adic analysis*, volume 4 of *Camb. Stud. Adv. Math.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- [35] Andrzej Szankowski. On Dvoretzky’s theorem on almost spherical sections of convex bodies. *Israel J. Math.*, 17:325–338, 1974.
- [36] S. J. Szarek. On the best constants in the Khinchin inequality. *Studia Math.*, 58(2):197–208, 1976.
- [37] Yasuo Yamasaki. A simple proof of Kwapien’s theorem. *Publ. Res. Inst. Math. Sci.*, 20:1247–1251, 1984.